

MEASUREMENT OF TRANSONIC AIRFLOW IN AN OSCILLATING BLADE CASCADE
WITH VARIABLE INTERBLADE PHASE ANGLE

Petr Šidlof

Technical University of Liberec
Liberec, Czech Republic

David Šimurda

Institute of Thermomechanics
Czech Academy of Sciences
Prague, Czech Republic

Jan Lepicovsky

Institute of Thermomechanics
Czech Academy of Sciences
Prague, Czech Republic

Martin Štěpán

Technical University of Liberec
Liberec, Czech Republic

Pavel Šidlof

Technical University of Liberec
Liberec, Czech Republic

ABSTRACT

The paper reports on a redesign of a test rig for investigation of flutter of turbomachinery blades in high-speed airflow, together with the first experimental results. The test section, mounted in the high-speed wind tunnel, consists of a linear cascade of five prismatic blades. A new mechanism was developed and tested, allowing controlled kinematic excitation of three middle blades with a continuously adjustable interblade phase angle (IBPA). The experimental setup is equipped with a laser triangulation sensor measuring the blade oscillation, unsteady pressure probes in the blade suction surface, strain-gauge bridges on the blade shafts monitoring the total torque and a schlieren optical setup with high-speed camera for visualization of the flow field around the middle blade. The measured data were analyzed for inlet Mach number of 1.09, frequency of blade oscillation of 150 Hz and interblade phase angles ranging from -90 deg to 180 deg. The pressure oscillation amplitude along the blade reached its maximum for $IBPA = -90$ deg at 40% of the chord length, and its minimum for $IBPA = +45$ deg. Among all measured cases, the most distinct behavior was observed when the blades oscillated out of phase ($IBPA = 180$ deg). In this condition, the normal shock on the pressure surface oscillated strongly from a point far downstream up to the leading edge, and the total torque exhibited the highest peak value.

Keywords: Blade Flutter, Aeroelasticity, Experimental Methods

NOMENCLATURE

f	frequency of blade oscillation [Hz]
c_p	pressure coefficient [1]
p_1	inlet static pressure [Pa]
p_i	local static pressure at i^{th} pressure tap [Pa]
M_1	inlet Mach number [1]
κ	specific heat ratio [1]
$IBPA$	interblade phase angle [deg]
k	reduced frequency (based on semi/chord) [1]
c	chord length [m]
u	flow velocity [m/s]

1. INTRODUCTION

Flow-induced vibration of turbomachinery blades continues to pose significant challenges in modern compressor and turbine designs. These vibrations, which are especially pronounced in the front stages of compressors and the aft stages of turbines, can induce high-cycle fatigue leading to eventual fracture, potentially resulting in catastrophic failures.

The issue of aeroelastic instability in turbomachines is not new. Despite decades of research and iterative improvements in design, current mitigation strategies often rely on avoiding operating regimes that are susceptible to flutter, rather than fully eliminating the phenomenon. This is particularly evident in high-efficiency machines featuring long and slender blades, which, due to their aerodynamic and structural characteristics, are more prone to flow-induced excitation. Fan and compressor blades are especially vulnerable because they encounter flow distortions

arising from environmental gusts, wake disturbances from nearby aircraft, or even foreign object impacts.

The underlying mechanics of flutter in turbomachinery are primarily associated with a dominant structural mode of blade oscillation. Unlike flutter in aircraft (wings, ailerons and control surfaces), the inherently higher stiffness and mass ratio of turbomachinery blades generally result in flow forces that have little effect on the natural mode shapes or frequencies. A blade within a bladed wheel does not undergo unstable oscillation in isolation: instead, flutter in turbomachinery manifests as a traveling wave characterized by an interblade phase angle (IBPA). The low internal damping within bladed discs renders aerodynamic damping the key stabilizing or destabilizing factor. This aerodynamic damping, which can be positive (dissipative) or negative (destabilizing), is influenced by unsteady aerodynamic effects. Once initiated, flutter in turbomachinery cannot be stopped in most cases and inevitably leads to failure [12].

An excellent review of computational prediction methods for aeroelasticity in turbomachinery was written by Marshall & Imregun [7] at Rolls-Royce and Imperial College. Marshall categorizes the methods into two major groups: classical, i.e. uncoupled methods (notably the eigensolution and energy methods), and integrated (strongly coupled) approaches. The energy method, which involves calculating the work of aerodynamic forces over one blade oscillation period for a range of interblade phase angles, remains arguably the most widely used technique for flutter prediction to date [13]. Recent advances in computational methodologies have further increased our ability to predict and analyze flutter phenomena in turbomachinery. While classical methods remain in use, high-fidelity computational fluid dynamics (CFD) tools now offer the potential to resolve complex unsteady aerodynamic phenomena accurately – for a review, see [1]. However, in transonic and supersonic operating conditions, the situation is complicated by shock wave oscillations, shock wave – boundary layer interactions and intermittent flow phenomena, which challenge even the most advanced computational models. Thus, the computational methods still require complementary experimental validation.

In open literature, there is a number of reports about test facilities for blade flutter research. However, only few dedicated test facilities in the world can operate for transonic flow velocities and reduced frequencies above 0.2. Such facilities are mostly linear cascades, although some semi- or fully-circular cascade facilities have been built. Among the leading world research laboratories are EPFL Lausanne in Switzerland [15], KTH Stockholm in Sweden [14,3], TU Darmstadt [2] or the NASA Glenn Research Center in Cleveland, Ohio [4].

During recent years, a new test facility for the investigation of blade flutter was designed and built at the Institute of Thermomechanics of the Czech Academy of Sciences [6]. The setup consists of a linear cascade of five compressor blade profiles, and in the first version it featured the possibility of high-frequency kinematic excitation of the middle blade. In the

current paper, a new drive mechanism capable of exciting three blades with an adjustable interblade phase angle is described, along with the first measurement results obtained under transonic flow conditions.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experimental setup consists of a rectangular test section (width 160 mm, height 195 mm) installed in an blow-down suction-type wind tunnel (see Fig. 1).

FIGURE 1: TEST SECTION WITH THE BLADES AND THE KINEMATIC EXCITATION

The blade cascade mounted in the wind tunnel test section is composed of five prismatic blades with a chord length of 120 mm and a transonic compressor blade profile published by Schreiber and Starke [8]. The blades are fabricated from ultra-high-strength steel to withstand high-frequency oscillation. Three of the blades are kinematically excited in the torsional mode using the newly designed blade drive mechanism, which is described in the following subsection.

2.1 Design of the multi-blade drive

The blade motion is enforced by a high-speed asynchronous electric motor (300 – 24,000 rpm) and a set of four-bar mechanisms that transform the steady rotational motion into torsional (pitching) oscillation. Each mechanism is composed of an eccentric disk, high-strength aluminum alloy coupler and a variable-cross-section steel rocker with optimized moment of inertia (see Fig. 2). The amplitude of the oscillation of the rocker and blade, which can be adjusted in discrete steps by replacing the disk with one of different eccentricity, is currently set to 0.25° . The interblade phase angle can be adjusted continuously by rotating the eccentric disks relative to each other on the common shaft.

FIGURE 2: TEST SECTION WITH THE BLADES AND BLADE DRIVE MECHANISM

Compared to the previous one-blade drive design described in [5], the new mechanism not only allows kinematic excitation of three blades, but also eliminates sliding constraints, resulting in significantly reduced joint clearance. Further, the optimized geometry and mass balancing produce considerably lower forces, moments and potentially harmful vibration within the mechanism. This is especially important in the case of high-frequency excitation. Fig. 3 shows the total reaction forces in the blade drive mechanism for zero IBPA and oscillation frequency of $f = 320$ Hz.

FIGURE 3: POLAR DIAGRAM OF THE TOTAL REACTION FORCE IN THE BLADE DRIVE MECHANISM FOR ONE SHAFT REVOLUTION. $IBPA = 0^\circ$, $f = 320$ Hz.

Without counterbalancing, the system would be exposed to a rotating force with an amplitude of 623 N. With properly set counterbalances on the main shaft, the amplitude is reduced to 279 N. It should be noted that $IBPA = 0^\circ$ is actually close to the worst-case scenario, where the possible force reduction is only 50%. For other IBPA values, the counterbalances can reduce the forces even more effectively, reaching a maximum reduction of 96.8% at $IBPA = -94^\circ$ (see Fig. 4).

FIGURE 4: PERCENTUAL REDUCTION OF THE PEAK REACTION FORCE AS A FUNCTION OF IBPA. GREEN SEGMENTS DENOTE IBPA INTERVALS WHERE COUNTERBALANCING IS LESS EFFECTIVE (FORCE REDUCTION IS LOWER THAN 50%).

For adverse intervals of $IBPA = -174^\circ..124^\circ$ and $IBPA = 8^\circ..120^\circ$ (denoted in green), where counterbalancing is not effective and force amplitudes would remain high, reversed motor rotation can be used. Using this trick, blade oscillation with the desired IBPA is achieved while the system benefits from force reduction at the favorable, opposite-sign IBPA.

Kinematically, the blade drive mechanism was designed so that each blade performs harmonic angular oscillation. If all elements of the mechanism were ideally rigid and no backlash were present in the joints, the oscillation would be almost perfectly sinusoidal – see Fig. 5.

FIGURE 5: DEVIATION OF THE BLADE ANGULAR OSCILLATION FROM SINUSOIDAL COMPUTED FROM THE KINEMATIC ANALYSIS OF THE IDEALIZED RIGID MECHANISM

However, the mechanisms and blades behave as rigid bodies only for low-frequency oscillation, up to about 100 Hz [Lepicovsky2023]. As inertial forces scale with the square of frequency, and particularly when resonance of the system components is approached, the elastic deformations become significant. Numerical simulations and measurements have confirmed that the excitation frequency is eventually limited by the first natural frequency of the steel blade (367 Hz, see Fig. 6) and by the natural frequency of the blade-rocker-coupler assembly, which is 312 Hz. In practice, measurements were so far performed up to 300 Hz.

FIGURE 6: FIRST TWO EIGENMODES OF THE STEEL BLADE

2.2 Measurement methods

The instantaneous incidence angle during the torsional oscillation is calculated from the signal of the MicroEpsilon ILD2310-40 laser triangulation sensor focused on the point at mid-span of the leading edge of blade No. 3. To measure the torque on the blades, strain gauge bridges are installed on the shafts of blades No. 2, 3 and 4.

The inlet isentropic Mach number M_1 is determined from the mean pressure readings from two rows of sidewall static pressure taps located shortly upstream of the blade cascade. Further, the unsteady pressure is measured at seven surface taps on the suction side of blade No. 3 (at mid-span) using Kulite XCQ-IC-062-25A miniature pressure transducers, which are mounted flush in grooves machined from the pressure side of the blade (see Fig. 7). More details on the experimental setup used for blade oscillation and unsteady pressure measurements can be found in [6, 9].

FIGURE 7: CROSS-SECTION OF THE TEST BLADE WITH GROOVES FOR KULITE PRESSURE TRANSDUCERS ON THE PRESSURE SIDE AND PRESSURE TAPS ON THE SUCTION SIDE.

In addition to point pressure measurements, the flow field in the vicinity of blade No. 3 is visualized using a schlieren optical setup and high-speed camera described in [10, 11]. Recording the image data synchronously with pressure and blade oscillation measurements helps to reveal the dynamics of the shock waves, the evolution of the subsonic and supersonic regions and their effect on the Kulite pressure signals.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the first measurement campaign, the new three-blade drive was tested and the flow field was measured and analysed at isentropic inlet Mach number $M_1 = 1.09$, blade oscillation frequency $f = 150$ Hz and $IBPA = 0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, \pm 90$ and 180° . The values of inlet flow velocity u and blade oscillation

frequency f correspond to a reduced frequency (based on semi-chord) of

$$k = \frac{\pi f c}{u} = 0.17, \quad (1)$$

which lies in the range $k < 0.5$ where flutter may occur.

For the baseline case $IBPA = 0^\circ$, Fig. 8 shows the time history of the angular deflection, total torque and unsteady pressure at first pressure port on blade No. 3 (together with its amplitude spectrum). The blade oscillation is harmonic with the mid-span amplitude of about 0.36° , which is slightly higher than the amplitude 0.25° forced at the rocker by the excitation mechanism. The difference is caused by elastic deformations of the blade, which are already noticeable at 150 Hz. It can also be observed that the mean incidence angle during blade oscillation is offset by about 0.22° from the zero position due to the high-speed airflow, which induces non-zero net aerodynamic moment.

The signal from the strain gauge bridge, indicating the total torque (comprising the aerodynamic and inertial moments), oscillates between -2 and $+6$ N·m and is in phase with the angular displacement, while the pressure signal is almost out of phase. The pressure spectrum shows a clear peak at 150 Hz with an amplitude of 0.75 kPa.

FIGURE 8: ANGULAR DEFLECTION, TOTAL TORQUE AND UNSTEADY PRESSURE AT THE FIRST PRESSURE PORT ON BLADE NO. 3 FOR THE BASELINE CASE $IBPA = 0^\circ$.

The schlieren visualization of the instantaneous flow field for the same baseline case is shown in Fig. 9. The image reveals the instantaneous position of the bow shock and lip shock near the leading edge of blade No. 3, the normal shock wave terminating the supersonic region in the interblade passage and several weak shock reflections from the channel walls and neighboring blades. From the high-speed camera recordings of the unsteady flow field, it can be seen that the normal shock oscillates irregularly between about 15% and 22% of the blade chord even for a static, non-oscillating cascade. When the three blades of the cascade start to oscillate, the range of the normal shock oscillation extends even further both upstream and downstream, depending on the *IBPA*.

FIGURE 9: FIELD OF VIEW AND THE SHOCK WAVE STRUCTURE VISUALIZED BY THE SCHLIEREN SETUP (*IBPA* = 0°)

The extreme upstream and downstream positions of the normal shock wave are listed in Tab. 1 for all the investigated interblade phase angles. For most cases, the normal shock moves between about 15% and 30% of the chord. For the case of *IBPA* = 180°, however, the normal shock travels upstream almost up to the leading edge, where it merges with the lip shock, and later downstream further than 33% of the chord, where it is not any more visible due to the bridge supporting the blades.

TABLE 1: UPSTREAM AND DOWNSTREAM EXTREME POSITIONS OF THE NORMAL SHOCK WAVE (NORMALIZED BY CHORD LENGTH), IDENTIFIED ALONG THE PRESSURE SIDE OF BLADE NO. 3 DURING CASCADE OSCILLATION AT VARIOUS INTERBLADE PHASE ANGLES.

<i>IBPA</i> [deg]	-90	-45	0	+45	+90	180
$x_{upstream}/c$	0.12	0.14	0.16	0.17	0.13	0.06
$x_{downstream}/c$	0.30	0.29	>0.33	0.29	0.29	>0.33

The pressure signals measured using the seven Kulite pressure probes on the suction surface of blade No. 3 were first processed using the phase-averaging procedure described in [9]. The amplitudes of the resulting phase-averaged waveforms are plotted in Fig. 10 in the form of dimensionless pressure coefficient

$$c_p = \frac{p_i - p_1}{0.5 \kappa p_1 M_1^2}, \quad (2)$$

where p_i is the amplitude of the phase-averaged pressure waveform at pressure port i and p_1 the inlet static pressure. Fig. 10 demonstrates that for negative *IBPA*, highest pressure oscillations are present at $x/c = 0.4$ (pressure tap d5) for *IBPA* = -45°. Qualitatively, all interblade phase angles measured result in similar pressure oscillation amplitude profiles, except for the extreme case *IBPA* = 180°, where the three blades oscillate entirely out of phase. In this case (light blue curve in Fig. 10), the highest pressure amplitude was measured further downstream, beyond the blade pivot point, at $x/c = 0.65$ (pressure tap d6).

FIGURE 10: PRESSURE COEFFICIENT AMPLITUDE ON THE SUCTION SIDE OF THE MIDDLE BLADE FOR *IBPA* = -90..180°.

The unsteady pressure measurements are robust, reliable, and provide high temporal resolution. However, the information is available only at seven discrete points on a single surface of one blade. Thus, spatial resolution is limited and evaluation of the overall aerodynamic force and moment on the blade by

interpolation and integration is challenging and rather inaccurate. Nevertheless, the experimental setup also provides signal from the torsion strain gauge bridge on the drive shaft of the blades. This signal measures the total torque on the blade, comprising the inertial and aerodynamic moment.

The phase-averaged total torques on the middle blade (No. 3) during one oscillation period are plotted in Fig. 11 for all measured interblade phase angles. Because the inertial moment remains identical regardless of the *IBPA*, the differences between the waveforms in Fig. 11 indicate the variations between the aerodynamic moment waveforms.

As with the unsteady pressure measurements, the total torque waveforms for *IBPA* = 0, +45, +90° are quite similar. Compared to the baseline case *IBPA* = 0°, the strongest differences can be observed for *IBPA* = -45°. In this case, the waveform is asymmetric with the positive peak significantly wider than the negative one. Another pronounced difference occurs for *IBPA* = 180°. Here, the torque reaches the highest measured value of 6.5 N · m and shows the opposite asymmetry (negative peak wider than the positive one). This is most likely because at *IBPA* = 180° the geometry of the interblade passage varies most during blade oscillations. Additionally, the schlieren visualizations revealed that in this case, the normal shock wave oscillates within the widest horizontal range in this case. Since the airflow upstream of the normal shock is supersonic (low static pressure) and downstream of the shock wave subsonic (high static pressure), the normal shock oscillation causes significant variations in the pressure load on the blade.

FIGURE 11: TOTAL TORQUE MEASURED BY THE STRAIN GAUGE BRIDGE ON BLADE NO. 3 DURING ONE OSCILLATION PERIOD. PHASE-AVERAGED VALUES FOR *IBPA* = -90° .. 180°

4. CONCLUSION

The test rig for the research of flutter in blade cascades was redesigned with a new blade drive mechanism for kinematic excitation of three blades. The drive was optimized for mass

balancing, reduction of joint clearance and potentially harmful vibration within the mechanism. It also allows quick and continuous adjustment of the interblade phase angle and stepwise setting of the blade oscillation amplitude.

Unsteady pressures on the blade surface, total torque on the blade and flow field visualizations were recorded for two transonic regimes $M_1 = 0.9$ and 1.09 , six interblade phase angles and blade oscillation frequencies $f = 10, 20, 50, 100$ and 150 Hz. For the configurations analyzed in this paper ($M_1 = 1.09$ and $f = 150$ Hz), the pressure oscillation amplitude along the blade is highest for *IBPA* = -45° at $x/c = 0.4$ and lowest for *IBPA* = 45°. Out of the analyzed cases, the most distinct behavior was observed when the blades oscillate fully out of phase, i.e. at *IBPA* = 180°. In this case, the normal shock on the pressure surface oscillates strongly from the point far downstream up to the leading edge, and the total torque reaches the highest peak value.

In the near future, the measured dataset will be thoroughly analyzed for all the other oscillation frequencies and also for the lower inlet Mach number $M_1 = 0.9$.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research was supported by grant No. LUAUS23231 *Origins and mechanisms of flutter and non-synchronous vibration in modern turbomachines operating at wide range of regimes.*

REFERENCES

- [1] Casoni, M., Benini, E., 2021. A review of computational methods and reduced order models for flutter prediction in turbomachinery. *Aerospace* 8, 242.
- [2] Holzinger, F., Wartzek, F., Jüngst, M., Schiffer, H.-P., Leichtfuss, S., 2016. Self-Excited Blade Vibration Experimentally Investigated in Transonic Compressors: Rotating Instabilities and Flutter. *Journal of Turbomachinery* 138, 041006.
- [3] Glodic, N., Tavera Guerrero, C., Gutierrez Salas, M., 2022. Blade oscillation mechanism for aerodynamic damping measurements at high reduced frequencies. *E3S Web Conf.* 345, 03002.
- [4] Lepicovsky, J., Chima, R.V., McFarland, E.R., Wood, J.R., 2001. On Flowfield Periodicity in the NASA Transonic Flutter Cascade. *Journal of Turbomachinery* 123, 501–509.
- [5] Lepicovsky, J., Šidlof, P., Šimurda, D., Štěpán, M., Luxa, M., 2021. New test facility for forced blade flutter research, in: *AIP Conference Proceedings*. AIP Publishing, p. 030001
- [6] Lepicovsky, J., Šimurda, D., Kielb, R.E., Šidlof, P., Štěpán, M. (2023). “Quasi-Dynamic Approximation of Unsteady Pressure Distribution for Transonic Airfoils in Flutter”. *Journal of Turbomachinery* 145.
- [7] Marshall, J.F., Imregun, M. (1996). “Advanced

- aeroelastic methods for turbomachinery blades”. *Journal of Fluids Structures*, 10(4), pp. 545–571.
- [8] Schreiber, H.A., Starke, H. (1984). “Experimental Cascade Analysis of a Transonic Compressor Rotor Blade Section”. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power* 106, pp. 288–294.
- [9] Šidlof, P., Šimurda, D., Lepicovsky, J., Štěpán, M., Vomáčko, V. (2023). “Flutter in a simplified blade cascade: Limits of the quasi-steady approximation”. *Journal of Fluids and Structures* 120, 103913
- [10] Šimurda, D., Psota, P., Šidlof, P., Kielb, R., Luxa, M., Hála, J., Lepicovsky, J., 2023. Optical measurement and visualization of transonic airflow in a compressor blade cascade. *Journal of Visualization* 26, 529–549.
- [11] Šimurda, D., Fürst, J., Musil, J., Šidlof, P., Lepicovsky, J., 2025. Aerodynamic response of a blade cascade to torsional excitation of one blade at subsonic and transonic velocities. *Propulsion and Power Research* 14, 259–273.
- [12] Srinivasan, A.V., 1997. Flutter and resonant vibration characteristics of engine blades. In: *ASME Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea and Air, Volume 497-GT-533*. American Society of Mechanical Engineers
- [13] Vedenev, V.V., Kolotnikov, M., Makarov, P., 2015. Experimental validation of numerical blade flutter prediction. *Journal of Propulsion and Power* 31, 1281–1291.
- [14] Vogt, D.M., Fransson, T.H., 2006. Experimental investigation of mode shape sensitivity of an oscillating low-pressure turbine cascade at design and off-design conditions. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power* 129, 530–541.
- [15] Zanker, A., Ott, P., Calza, P., 2013. Experimental aeroelastic analysis of clustered turbine blades vibrating in mixed Torsion/Bending mode, in: *31st AIAA Applied Aerodynamics Conference*.